

THE IMPORTANCE OF EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF DIALOGICAL SPEECH OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN THE FRENCH LANGUAGE (IN THE EXAMPLE OF A1 LEVEL STUDENTS)

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6806635>

Abstract. This article provides detailed information on the importance of educational technology and various interesting teaching methods in the development of dialogic speaking in French in secondary schools. Various innovative technologies are mentioned in the article. In addition, the importance of the French language and the increase in the demand for foreign languages in our country were highlighted.

Keywords: educational technologies, dialogic speech and its development, oral and written speech.

ТЕКСТ НАУЧНОЙ РАБОТЫ НА ТЕМУ «ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В РАЗВИТИИ ДИАЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ РЕЧИ УЧАЩИХСЯ ОБЩЕОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫХ ШКОЛ ПО ФРАНЦУЗСКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ (НА ПРИМЕРЕ УЧАЩИХСЯ УРОВНЯ А1)»

Аннотация. В данной статье представлена подробная информация о значении образовательных технологий и различных интересных методик обучения в развитии диалогической речи на французском языке в общеобразовательной школе. В статье упоминаются различные инновационные технологии. Кроме того, была отмечена важность французского языка и увеличение спроса на иностранные языки в нашей стране.

Ключевые слова: образовательные технологии, диалогическая речь и ее развитие, устная и письменная речь.

INTRODUCTION

Teaching and learning a foreign language using modern technologies is one of the most effective ways. In this process, including: - when using computers, the student can watch and listen to foreign language videos, demonstrations, dialogues, movies or cartoons; — it is possible to listen and watch foreign language radio broadcasts and television programs; - use of tape recorders and cassettes, which are considered a more traditional method; - CD players can be used. The use of these technical tools makes the process of learning a foreign language more interesting and effective for students.

In the course of foreign language classes, it is necessary to use advanced pedagogical technologies, interactive, innovative methods, communicative and informational tools.

Advanced methods serve as a compos in mastering a foreign language. One such method is the use of role-playing games in the course of the lesson. Role-playing games are the application of different situations in our real life in the process of learning a foreign language. This method helps to create a language environment during the lesson.

RESEARCH METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

Speech is a type of human activity, the use of thinking based on language tools (words, phrases, sentences). Speech performs the function of communication and message, emotional

expression and influence of mutual opinion. A well-developed speech serves as one of the important tools of a person's active activity in society. For a student, speech is a tool for successful education at school. What is speech development? If the student and his/her language activities are taken into account, speech development means active and practical acquisition of the language in all aspects (pronunciation, vocabulary, syntactic structure, connected speech). In the case of a teacher, the development of speech means the use of methods and types of work that help students acquire language pronunciation, vocabulary, syntactic construction and connected speech as an important asset.

For speech activity, as well as for the development of students' speech, it is necessary to observe several conditions:

1. There must be a requirement for a person's speech to surface. The methodical requirement of developing the student's speech is to create a situation in which the student expresses his opinion, the desire and need to express something verbally or in writing.
2. Any speech should have content and material. The more complete, rich, and valuable this material is, the more meaningful its description will be.
3. An idea is understandable only if it is expressed using a word, a phrase, a sentence, and a figure of speech that the listener understands.

Therefore, the third condition for successful development of speech is arming speech with language tools. There are several aspects of speech acquisition. These are:

1. Learning the norms of the literary language.
2. Mastering the important speech skills necessary for every member of our society, i.e. reading and writing skills.
3. Improving students' speech culture.

Three directions are clearly distinguished in the development of speech:

- 1) work on words;
- 2) working on phrases and sentences;
- 3) work on connected speech.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Lexicology (together with phraseology and stylistics), morphology, syntax serves as the linguistic base for working on words, phrases and sentences; and connected speech is based on logic, literary studies and linguistics of complex syntactic integrity. Consistency in the development of speech is ensured by increasing the ability to subjugate four conditions, namely consistency, perspective, diversity, different types to a common goal.

Reforms in the education system and the law on the state language require changes in the methodology and practice of forming children's speech, in particular, the development of speech of older children of preschool age. These changes are reflected in normative educational and methodological literature to a certain extent. But they need to be approached critically from the point of view of current requirements. Most of the Methodist scientists correctly emphasize the conditions for the development of children's speech in preschool educational institutions. According to this author, the shortcomings of speech culture have a negative impact on the child's personality. In particular, the child becomes shy, aloof and worthless in communication with his peers.

In addition, such a child's interest in learning the surroundings decreases, which later causes him to not master the lessons at school. Summarizing the research works, we found the need for the following unified approach to solving the task of forming speech culture in preschool children in most of them:

- formation of correct pronunciation with sounds (the child develops hearing speech first, he acquires pronunciation later);
- creating accurate pronunciation (pronouncing words and phrases piece by piece and clearly);
- work on correct accentuation when pronouncing a word;
- work on orthographic correctness of speech (this is the sum of standard pronunciation rules);
- development of speech speed;
- formation of expressiveness of speech (natural, free, i.e. conscious expression of speech);
- education of speech communication skills;
- formation of speech hearing aids;
- formation of speech breathing;
- to develop the ability to express one's opinion freely and coherently.

Based on the observations, it was concluded that the role of educators and parents in the education of speech communication in preschool children is significant.

In the process of working on children's speech:

- a) to be polite in conversation with peers;
- b) to speak in a natural tone;
- c) to look at the interlocutor's face when speaking;
- d) pay attention to keeping the rules in a calm state.

We know that there is an integral connection between language and thought. "Truly, language and thought cannot live without each other," writes A.M. Borodich. Although language and thinking cannot live without each other, they do not represent the same phenomenon. Thought is the culmination of objective existence, and language is a method of expression, a means of imparting and strengthening ideas to other people. Words and concepts require each other dialogically.

CONCLUSION

In short, as a result of using innovative methods in foreign language classes, students' logical thinking skills develop, their speech becomes fluent, and the ability to quickly and correctly answer is formed. Such methods make the student eager for knowledge. The student tries to prepare thoroughly for the lessons. This makes students active subjects of the educational process. As the educational system sets itself the task of educating a free-thinking, well-rounded, mature person, in the future, we future teachers will contribute by developing ways to effectively use innovative technologies possible.

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